

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF CUSTOMS TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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***Abstract:** This article investigates the integral and differential characteristics of English customs phrases as they appear in translation that these terms reflect new semantic meanings of the terminological system, the challenge of adequate translation of English customs terms brought into the terminological system based on cognition has become especially essential at this time. The importance of producing a bilingual English and Uzbek dictionary of customs terminology is stressed in the essay.*

***Keywords:** lexicology, system of term development in customs affairs, stylistics and semantics of translation, terminological system, customs, product, custom sphere*

Over the last decade, one of the most important fields of linguistic research has been the description and analysis of scientific and technical word systems. The interest in specific terminology issues is explained by the growing importance of terminology and its various directions in the field of standardization. In many ways, conducting linguistic research targeted at eliminating discrepancies between language and special-science disciplines, as well as language barriers encountered in special-professional activities, is critical to the process of regulating the scientific and technological level. The study of Customs terminology from a young perspective from a linguistic standpoint determines its importance around the world.

Because there is a direct general linguistic connection, there is a lexical-semantic process between English and Uzbek customs terminology and common literary language. Expression that contribute to the stylistically colored and

appealing representation of speech. They basically make the language of art works in literature more appealing. In the English terminology of the customs sector, we can see the existence of aesthetically tinted phrases. They are employed as a type of combined special term and are strongly linked to the terms of the customs sphere.

Accreditation – registration of the legal entity or the private enterprise in customs bodies of Uzbek, after realization of accreditation the enterprise has the right to be engaged in foreign trade.

Accreditation customs - the customs body of Uzbek in which is accredited Uzbek subject of foreign trade.

Allowing documents – licences, certificates, permissions and other documents of the State Services necessary for finishing customs registration of goods.

The authorized bank – any commercial bank officially registered in territory of Uzbek which has the license of National bank of Uzbek for carrying out of currency transactions, and also carries out currency control of operations of the clients.

Area of operations of customs – an administrative and territorial unit of Uzbek in which territory the customs carries out the activity. Consignment is the act of consigning, which is placing any material in the hand of another, but retaining ownership until the goods are sold or person is transferred.

The commission contract – the contract at which one party (commission agent) undertakes on the instructions of other party (commitment) for corresponding compensation to make one or several legal actions on its own behalf but at the expense of the commitment.

Wholesale (Ulgurji sotuvchi)

A person or company who intends to sell products en masse from different vendors, who in turn sell them to consumers. Distributors and wholesalers usually work as partners through a single channel.

Customer Lifetime Value (Xaridorning umr bo'yi qiymati)

It is the prediction of future income or profit, the value produced by the consumer throughout the entire relationship with the trader, and the net profit.

Production rate (Ishlab chiqarish darajasi)

This is a measure that is part of other measurements used to assess the health of e-commerce. This is calculated by dividing the number of people who performed a particular action by the number of visitors to a particular page or process.

Search page optimization (Qidiruv sahifasini optimallashtirish)

It is the process of creating, tracking and customizing landing pages to maximize traffic conversion.

Customer segmentation (Mijozlarni segmentatsiyalash)

This means targeting the customers who bring the most revenue and have the highest revenue potential. These can include repeat buyers, average order values, customers who submit a review, as well as customers who respond to offers and promotions.

The five sub-headings were used to classify frequent literary terms. Now we'll look at how they work in both the common literary and TC terminological systems:

- **CARGO DECLARATION**

Information submitted prior to or on arrival or departure of a means of transport for commercial use that provides the particulars required by the Customs relating to cargo brought to or removed from the Customs territory. For example

The nature and contents of Cargo declarations may vary from country to country according to the commercial means of transport used. The particulars of the cargo (freight) may include kind, number, marks and numbers of packages, brief description of the goods, gross weight, etc. In some countries, these particulars may be submitted by electronic means.

- **COMPENSATING PRODUCTS**

Products :

(a) obtained within a country resulting from the manufacturing, processing or repair of the goods for which the use of the inward processing procedure is authorized;

- (b) obtained abroad and resulting from the manufacturing, processing or repair of goods for which the use of the outward processing procedure is authorized. For example:

In some countries the products obtained from the treatment of imported, exported or domestic goods identical in description, quality and technical characteristics to those temporarily admitted for inward processing or temporarily exported for outward processing, as the case may be, are deemed to be compensating products.

- **COUNTRY OF ORIGIN OF GOODS**

Country in which the goods have been produced or manufactured, according to the criteria laid down for the purposes of application of the Customs tariff, of quantitative restrictions or of any other measure related to trade. For example:

In this definition the word "country" may include a group of countries, a region or a part of a country.

CUSTOMS

The Government Service which is responsible for the administration of Customs law and the collection of duties and taxes and which also has the responsibility for the application of other laws and regulations relating to the importation, exportation, movement or storage of goods. For example:

This term is also used when referring to any part of the Customs Service or its main or subsidiary offices.

This term is also used adjectivally in connection with officials of the Customs, duties and taxes or control on goods, or any other matter within the purview of the Customs (Customs officer, Customs duties, Customs office, Customs declaration).

- **CUSTOMS CLEARING AGENT**

A person who carries on the business of arranging for the Customs clearance of goods and who deals directly with the Customs for and on behalf of another person.

Examples of Customs clearing agents are Customs agents, Customs brokers and freight forwarders.

Some countries require that Customs clearing agents or Customs brokers be approved or licensed by the Customs.

See also the term "Third party".

It is clear that taking a position as terminological units and perform the function of terms as a consequence of the link of lexical creation of common literary language with terms of customs, as a result of semantic qualities, metaphorical transfer, and stylistic coloring. Given the difficulty of translating stylistically colored terms with figurative meaning from one language to another, the unification of custom terms, the avoidance of heterogeneity in terminology, and the clarification of the most optimal terms among the sphere terms, proper alternative selection has become an important and urgent task of today. According to terminology rules, we may reject different interpretations of the translation of English and Uzbek customs terms.

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